

COMMUNITY SERVICE TEACHING PRACTICE AS AN EFFORT TO IMPROVE SKILLS AND EXPERIENCE AT THE PRIVATE HIGH SCHOOL OF PEMATANG SIANTAR

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Abstract

The Community Service (PKM) Teaching Practice Activity as an Effort to Improve Skills and Experience aims to improve teachers' skills and understanding in compiling scientific papers according to academic principles. This activity is designed to provide the knowledge and skills needed by teachers in the process of writing scientific papers, which is an important aspect in the development of educator professionalism. PPL (Field Experience Practice) is a method of equipping educational students while preparing them to become professional educational personnel. On this occasion I chose to do field experience practice at SMA Swasta Teladan Pematangsiantar which is located at Jl.Singosari No.03 Kel.Bantan, West Siantar, Pematang Siantar. and has been approved by the UHN PPL coordinator to host PPL in 2025. The purpose of the PPL program is to provide opportunities for students to learn about experiencing and living in schools or learning problems related to institutions: improving students' ability to apply knowledge and Field Experience Practice (PPL) which will be completed in February 2025 includes the implementation of guided PPL 1 time. Although there are several challenges, the Field Experience Practice (PPL) Activities at SMA Swasta Teladan Pematangsiantar went smoothly. With the support and direction from various parties, especially the school itself, we were able to overcome the challenges we faced and greatly helped the smooth implementation of the PPL program at the school.

Keywords: Prospective Teachers, Field Experience Practice, Teaching Practice, Schools

INTRODUCTION

Law No. 14 of 2005 concerning teachers and lecturers firmly states that teachers are required to have academic qualifications, competencies, teacher certificates, and so on. Thus, teachers are required to master various abilities. One of the abilities that must be mastered is developing themselves professionally. The competency standards that teachers must have include four types of competencies, namely: pedagogical, personality, professional, and social competencies. Pedagogical competency is the ability to manage learning which includes understanding students, designing and implementing learning, evaluating learning outcomes, and developing students to actualize their various potentials. Personality competency is the ability of a strong, stable, mature, wise and authoritative personality, being a role model for students, and having noble morals.

Students in educational field practice must be fully prepared before entering the field. It's not just about acquiring knowledge for teaching; PLK students must also prepare themselves mentally, physically, and skillfully to meet their students. They must be mentally prepared, act like a teacher who is respected and emulated, and position themselves appropriately. They must also adopt the attitude, appearance, and language they will use in front of their students. PLK students must also be able to prepare their teaching materials, including learning materials, tools, and methods/methods to be used in the learning process. Education is a form of awareness and effort to create a fun and engaging learning environment for students, enabling them to actively learn. This enables them to develop their intelligence, self-development, morals, personality, skills, and religious beliefs. School education consists of a number of subjects that students must study, particularly economics, mathematics, and science.

Science learning will become the primary foundation of education because it plays a crucial role in developing and shaping students who think critically, logically, innovatively, creatively, and are competitive worldwide. Furthermore, science learning is expected to provide a platform for students to better understand science contextually and apply it to everyday life. Therefore, scientific literacy is essential for all students. This encompasses psychological activity, knowledge, and how to organize and measure it, all of which can be re-examined with curiosity, determination, and persistence. Understanding Field Experience Practice (PPL): 1) PPL is usually referred to as learning practice, and other activities related to learning in schools are carried out with guidance in accordance with teaching professional standards. 2) Field Experience Practice (PPL) is direct instruction for prospective teachers. The Faculty of Teacher Training and Education, HKBP Nommensen University, Pematang Siantar (FKIP UHKBNP) is an Educational Personnel Education Institution (LPTK) with a mission to develop professional teachers who have four teacher competencies, namely pedagogical competency, professional, social, and personality. In this regard, FKIP UHKBNP implements curriculum to help graduates achieve teacher competency. The Field Experience Program (PPL), an applied course designed to strengthen the foundation of work behavior and thus provide professional skills, is one component of the supporting course. Field Experience Programs (PPL) foster independence, responsibility, and problem-solving skills. They also offer the training and skills necessary for school administration and management, as well as the education sector. Therefore, students in this program are required to undertake school practice, teaching practice, and assist students experiencing learning difficulties in their field of study.

METHOD

Both the PPL implementing institution or unit and prospective student participants must know and be ready to face several things during the preparation stage. This consists of:

1. Participant Requirements

The following are the prerequisites that must be met by each PPL participant.

- a. Registered as a UHKBNP student in the semester in which PPL is held;
- b. Complete a minimum of 120 credits of study with the following GPA requirements:
Students who are doing odd semester internships have a minimum GPA of 3.00,
- c. Listing PPL courses on the KRS;
- d. Has passed the courses in Learning Planning, Teaching and Learning Strategies and Micro Teaching with a B grade.
- e. Willing to be placed in a school determined by the University.
- f. The location and area where students' PPL will be implemented are determined by the University or Students.

can choose/determine the PPL location according to the distance from where they live.

2. Students who wish to participate in the PPL program must first register as prospective PPL participants. Each study program has its own registration process. Registration times depend on the academic calendar. To complete registration, students must complete and submit the following form:

- a. Accurate participant biodata and signed according to the circumstances;
- b. Statement that the participant is willing to comply with PPL regulations; and
- c. Additional requirements set by the PPL team. Prospective PPL participants must be screened to ensure they have met the administrative requirements. The Study Program makes the decision, taking into account the following factors: type of school or institution; existing problems at the school or institution; and
- d. school or institution requirements, participants who meet the administrative requirements are divided into several groups.

3. The Attendance List briefing kept at the UHKBNP campus shows that students attended briefing for two days before PPL.

- a. The purpose of PPL provision is for students to understand and uphold the basic concepts, meanings, objectives, approaches, programs, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of PPL. They must also learn about the situations, conditions, potentials, and problems that may arise during PPL. They must also understand good school behavior and understand how educational institutions are managed and developed. have the resources and skills necessary to complete school projects and programs;

- b. Provision Materials: Provision materials include materials related to PPL and materials intended to increase students' understanding of how education is implemented in accordance with new education policies.

Figure 1. Learning process in the classroom

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of the Teaching Practice Program (PPL Mengajar) at SMA Swasta Teladan Pematangsiantar has provided numerous benefits for both students and the school. Academically, students gain real-world experience in teaching, developing learning materials, and addressing various challenges that arise in the classroom. Furthermore, the application of technology in learning is a crucial aspect in increasing teaching effectiveness and facilitating student understanding of the material. Before the training took place, the implementation of the community service/PPL was opened with a welcoming speech from the principal, Mr. Sangkot Sitohang, S.Si., M.Pd. Enthusiastically welcoming the PPL activities carried out by the PPL TEAM of HKBP Nommensen Pematangsiantar University. According to him, the activities carried out by the PPL TEAM are in line with the school's vision and mission to become a special driving school for grades X and XI who are required to learn by utilizing digital or internet media and others. The school has also facilitated by providing a special room, namely a digital class consisting of 1 digital class used alternately.

1. Results of program implementation

Analysis of the results of the Field Experience Practice (PPL) at the Exemplary Private High School in Pematang Siantar can be analyzed.

- a. Internship students gained a wealth of knowledge during their teaching practice at Teladan Private High School. As teachers, we must understand classroom situations and identify differences in student characteristics. A teacher must be able to make learning enjoyable and motivating.
- b. When conducting teaching practice at Exemplary Private High School, teachers must know what students need and what students should achieve when they study in class.
- c. During their teaching internship at Teladan Private High School, students gain a wealth of knowledge. As prospective teachers, they must interact with local teachers and their supervising teachers to ensure the classroom learning process runs smoothly and achieves both teacher and student goals.
- d. When conducting teaching internships with student interns, it's crucial to have specific interactions with students to keep them motivated to learn in class. They can build camaraderie and increase their desire to learn through interactions both inside and outside the classroom.
- e. In teaching practice at Teladan High School, PPL students can learn a lot about the importance of students participating in the learning process because they have the opportunity to express their thoughts and feelings about what they learn in class.

Analysis of the results of the Field Experience Practice (PPL) in the Economics Education, Mathematics Education, and Biology Education study programs at the Exemplary Private High School in Pematang Siantar can be analyzed

- a. In their teaching practice in Economics at the Pematangsiantar Private High School, the PPL students were able to teach students a great deal about the importance of economics, particularly in their daily lives. They were motivated by the importance of economic activities in their lives, both at school and in the community.
- b. During their teaching practice in mathematics at the exemplary private high school in Pematangsiantar, the interns were able to teach students a great deal about the importance of mathematics, especially in their daily lives. They were able to solve real-life problems related to the material.
- c. I teach students about real life, especially in Biology lessons. I create real-life examples so that students can easily understand them, for example about viruses, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, making it easier for students to understand biology material.

2. Recommendations and Improvement Proposals

During the PPL at SMA Swasta Teladan Pematang Siantar for approximately four months, students experienced many things, both pleasant and sad. Teachers must be able to master all the skills needed to be a teacher in their position as a teacher. A teacher must not only have knowledge of the subject matter, but must also have the ability to control the class and change students' views and behavior. Because it is an important thing that the author learned during PPL, a teacher must have the ability to control the class and maintain class balance so that the learning process runs well.

Figure 2: Group photo of the vice principal, supervising lecturer and students of HKBP Nomensen University, Pematangsiantar

CONCLUSION

The Field Experience Internship (PPL) at SMA Swasta Teladan Pematangsiantar provides students with real-world experience in understanding and carrying out the duties of a professional educator. Through this activity, students gain not only teaching skills but also classroom management, learning materials development, and student learning evaluation skills. During the PPL, students have the opportunity to observe student characteristics, interact directly in the school environment, and apply the educational theories they have learned. This activity also fosters self-confidence, creativity in delivering material, and the ability to adapt to various learning conditions. This in-depth activity successfully improved teachers' competency in understanding and implementing critical literacy approaches in the classroom. Teachers became better prepared to guide students in facing the challenges of the digital era, which is filled with complex and not always valid information. Overall, the internship program at SMA Swasta Teladan Pematangsiantar significantly contributes to improving the pedagogical, professional, social, and personal competencies of students as prospective teachers. Thus, the internship program serves as a crucial tool in preparing qualified educators who are ready to face the challenges of the ever-evolving world of education.

SUGGESTION

1. Special for Schools

- a. It is hoped that the school will continue to provide opportunities and support to PPL students in developing their teaching abilities and other professional skills.
- b. Coordination between mentor teachers and PPL students needs to be improved so that the mentoring process runs more effectively and in a focused manner.
- c. Learning facilities, such as media and classroom support facilities, should be continuously updated to support a more innovative learning process.

2. Exclusively for Universities

- a. Universities need to ensure that DPLs have sufficient time, adequate pedagogical competence, and the ability to provide constructive feedback to students during the PPL process.
- b. Creating a working relationship between Universities, Teachers, Schools and Schools.
- c. Supervise activities directly and indirectly

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